

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP AND WORK MOTIVATION WITH THE TEACHER'S PERFORMANCE OF PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOL IN SOUTH BANJARMASIN DISTRICT, INDONESIA

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Abstract:

Teacher performance is the level of success in completing teaching and work called the "level of performance" or level of work. The teacher's performance appears from his responsibilities as a teacher and educator in carrying out the mandate, the profession he embraces, and the moral he has, So that the teacher who has high performance is a teacher who has work productivity equal with standards that are determined and agreed upon in achieving school goals. In achieving high school goals / quality not only the role of the teacher but also the leadership role of principal and teacher motivation also very influential and dominant in the teacher's performance so that they can achieve goals that have been jointly shared. The research aims to find out: (1) the relationship between transformational leadership and the teacher's performance of State Elementary School in South Banjarmasin District. (2) Work motivation and the teacher's performance of Public Elementary School in South Banjarmasin District. (3) Simultaneous relationship between transformational leadership and work motivation with the teacher's performance of State Elementary School in South Banjarmasin District. The research design uses quantitative research with correlational methods. The subjects of the study were 404 elementary school teachers with the status of civil servants (PNS) totaling 404 teachers. The sampling technique in this study is proportional. As for the number of samples determined using the Slovin formula obtained a sample of 201 teachers. Data collection techniques are questionnaires conducted by distributing written questionnaires containing statements, and answered by respondents. The results showed that: (1) There was a positive relationship between transformational leadership and teacher's performance. (2) There is a positive relationship between work motivation and teacher's performance. (3) There is a

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simultaneous positive relationship between transformational leadership and work motivation with teacher's performance.

Keywords: transformation leadership, work motivation, teacher performance

1. Introduction

In achieving high school goals/quality not only the role of the teacher but also the principal's leadership role is also very influential and dominant in advancing the school itself so Dimyanti (2014), said the elements that underlie leadership in achieving goals are ability to influence others (group/subordinate), ability to direct or motivate the behavior of others or groups and the element of cooperation to achieve the desired goals.

At this level, the principal as an education leader is a formal leader (Formally Designated Leader) by the organization concerned or the organization that is his boss. While the teacher (educator), according to Law No. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System, Chapter XI article 39 that educators are professionals who are tasked with planning and implementing the learning process, assessing learning outcomes, conducting guidance and training, as well as conducting research and community service, especially the educator section in universities.

The teacher is one of the education personnel as a determining factor for the success of the school's objectives besides other education personnel, because the teacher who is directly in contact with the students, to provide guidance whose estuary will produce the expected output Priansa (2014). One of the legal umbrella in strengthening the above statement is Permendiknas No. 16/2007: that teachers need to have a minimum standard of certain competencies in carrying out their teaching duties. Competency standards are expected to be the background of the realization of teacher performance, as well as an effort to improve the quality of education outcomes of students Hamzah (2008). To that end, teacher performance must be improved and developed as an effort to tightly control school education, efforts to improve performance are usually done by giving motivation in the form of rewards or intensive and others so that it can improve the quality of performance in educating children in school.

One of the ways to improve teacher performance is also work motivation where in the work of course someone teaching or educator wants to achieve goals that have been determined and set together, in achieving school goals and it needs to process, as for the process of work motivation there are rewards and achievements, recognition and also in the form of rewards Wahjosumidjo (2008). That other than also needed job security and can also be support from leaders which are included in intrinsic motivation where all the things that drive us to work better and harder are summarized in the goals we achieve then try new things and challenge in the teaching work we carry out in school and extrinsic where all things that can motivate but come not from

ourselves, but from the environment or others such as salary or payment that suits our performance in work or teaching, a conducive work environment where the kit colleagues a mutual support and also help each other to develop, it would be nice if our coworkers were not limited to friends in school but also our good friends a day outside of school, boss or leader in this case the principal who was the role model where the boss or leader was not a "boss" but being a leader who is able to give change and protect subordinates at school, when a boss or a leader comes early and goes home late, when the boss wants to help us in developing and succeeding in getting a better career and also important is appreciation or recognition from boss when we finish work that produces achievements both for school and for the students we train. which is what Maslow put forward in the theory of needs. Work motivation is very closely related to leadership, this is expressed in Herzberg's theory where a boss always cooperates with his subordinates in achieving high performance to achieve goals that have been compromised, thus it is clear that work motivation is also very closely related in performance, especially teachers in teaching and children's education at school.

With the above description it is clear that researchers choose transformational leadership and work motivation on teacher performance, because the creativity of teacher performance in an education depends on how the principal is in managing, both in planning, organizing, leading (directing), and controlling and also motivating from superiors in improving teacher performance. Therefore, principals are required to apply leadership correctly and consequently and motivate them in teaching and education (Teacher Performance).

2. Methods

Based on the research plan to be achieved, this study is intended to find out the relationship between transformational leadership and work motivation with the performance of public elementary school teachers in the sub-district of South Banjarmasin. Banjarmasin City. The method used in this research is quantitative research with relationship analysis method (correlation). The correlation is a form of data analysis in research that aims to determine the strength or shape of the direction of the relationship between two or more variables, and the magnitude of the effect caused by the independent variable on the dependent variable (Siregar, 2013).

The relationship between one with several other variables is expressed by the magnitude of the correlation coefficient and the significance/statistical significance. The existence of a correlation between two or more variables does not mean that there is an influence or causal relationship of a variable on other variables.

The research variables include two independent variables, namely transformational leadership (X1), work motivation (X2) and the dependent variable of teacher performance (Y). The relationship between these variables can be described in the constellation of problems as follows:

- The relationship between transformational leadership (X1) and teacher's performance (Y).
- The relationship between work motivation (X2) and teacher performance (Y)
- The relationship between transformational leadership (X1) and work motivation (X2) together with teacher performance (Y)

3. Population and Sample

3.1 Population

Population is used to mention allied/groups of objects that are the target of the research, then the researcher has two: 1). Finite population means the number of individuals is determined. 2). Infinite population means that the number of individuals is infinite or unknown. With the two types of population above, the researcher takes on the first point, namely the finite population, where the number of objects is from State Elementary School Teachers in South Banjarmasin District with the status of civil servants (Civil Servants) with a number of 404 male teachers 133 people, teachers women 271 people, then the State Elementary School is divided into 7 District Clusters.

3.2 Sample

This sampling technique is probability sampling that each member of the population has the same opportunity to be selected as a sample.

Determine the number of samples in this study using the Slovin formula. (Siregar, 2014: 34) as follows:

$$n = N / (1 + Ne^2)$$

Where:

n = sample

N = population

e = estimated error rate

Researchers took the total population of State Primary School teachers in the seven South Banjarmasin Sub-District Clusters of N = 404, 5% error tolerance limit, so obtained the required sample number 201.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Results

A. Characteristics of Respondents

The results of data collection carried out on 201 teachers who were made as respondents obtained the characteristics of respondents based on age.

B. Explanation of Respondents

In this study, the dependent variable (dependent variable) is the teacher's performance (Y) and the two independent variables (independent variables) consisting of: transformational leadership variables (X1) and work motivation (X2).

C. Classic Assumption Testing

Before testing the hypothesis, a classical assumption is first tested that is intended to ensure that the correlation model can be used or not. If the classical assumption test has been fulfilled, a classic test kit can be used.

1. Normality Test

2. Homogeneity test

D. Hypothesis Testing

1. Partial Test

Partial test to examine how independent variables relate individually to the dependent variable clearly as follows:

a. Transformational Leadership Relationships (X1) on the Quality of Teacher Performance (Y)

b. The Relationship of Work Motivation (X2) to the Quality of Teacher Performance (Y)

2. Simultaneous Test

Simultaneous test results of the variables of transformational leadership, work motivation and teacher performance can be seen in table 4.6 below:

Table 4.6: Simultaneous Test Results

		Correlations		
		Kinerja Guru	Kepemimpinan Transformasional	Motivasi Kerja
Kinerja Guru	Pearson Correlation	1	.743**	.754**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000
	N	201	201	201
Kepemimpinan Transformasional	Pearson Correlation	.743**	1	.529**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000
	N	201	201	201
Motivasi Kerja	Pearson Correlation	.754**	.529**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	201	201	201

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Based on Table 4.6 above, the result of the correlation between transformational leadership and teacher performance is 529 with a sig value of .000 This shows that the relationship of transformational leadership to teacher performance is positive and strong in the same direction.

The correlation between work motivation and teacher performance is 1 with a sig .000 value, this shows that the relationship between teacher motivation and teacher performance is positive and strong in the same direction.

The sig (2tailed) results obtained from .000 means that Ho is rejected, which means that the entire study is statistically significant and has a positive (unidirectional) correlation.

Thus Ho, who stated that transformational leadership and work motivation together had no relationship to teacher performance in SDN in South Banjarmasin District, was rejected, meaning that Ha, who stated transformational leadership and work motivation together, had a significant influence on the quality of teacher performance. in SDN in South Banjarmasin Subdistrict received.

5. Conclusion

The conclusions from this study show several things, including: (1) There is a positive relationship between transformational leadership and teacher performance. (2) There is a positive relationship between work motivation and teacher performance. (3) There is a simultaneous positive relationship between transformational leadership and work motivation with teacher performance.

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